

Breaking the Silence: Understanding Cancer-Related Stigma among Tertiary Students in Punjab

Dr Eric Kwasi Elliason¹, Dr Kulvir Singh², Dr Ajit Pal Singh³

¹ *Teaching Assistant, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, Desh Bhagat University,
Punjab*

² *Dr Kulvir Singh, Associate Professor, Desh Bhagat University, Punjab*

³ *Dr Ajit Pal Singh, Associate Professor, Desh Bhagat University, Punjab*

Corresponding Email: manericus2017@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Cancer stigma has a profound impact on the psychological and social well-being of survivors, affecting their reintegration into society and access to care. India experiences a high stigma towards people suffering from chronic diseases, especially cancer. This study was conducted in Punjab to assess various stigmas and misconceptions about cancer among tertiary students in Punjab, India.

Aim: This study examined cancer stigma and misconceptions among tertiary students regarding people living with cancer in Punjab. It aimed to pinpoint drivers of stigma and misconceptions that may guide interventions and support attitude building.

Methods: A cross-sectional descriptive design was used, and 601 tertiary students were recruited from six districts of Punjab (Patiala, Mansa, Sangrur, Tarn Taran, Gurdaspur, and Shri Muktsar). The Cancer Stigma Scale was adopted for data collection using a structured questionnaire. SPSS was used to describe stigma patterns and associated beliefs via various descriptive and inferential statistical techniques.

Results: 53.4% of respondents disagreed that cancer so adversely affects a cancer survivor's life that they can never return to normal, and 63.4% of respondents agreed that cancer adversely affects a cancer survivor's relationship with other individuals. Furthermore, 46.3% of participants agreed that cancer patients are responsible for their own illnesses. Two-thirds of students (68%) agreed that cancer commonly ends a career, indicating strongly ingrained stigmatizing notions. The present study results emphasize the fact that tertiary students in Punjab still suffer from the stigma and misconceptions attached to cancer.

Conclusion: Cancer-related stigma remains a pervasive issue among tertiary students in Punjab, influenced by cultural beliefs, limited awareness, and misconceptions. Addressing these attitudes requires targeted educational campaigns, survivor advocacy, and interventions emphasizing recovery, resilience, and inclusion. Such efforts are crucial to reducing stigma, fostering empathy, and improving the social reintegration of cancer survivors.

Keywords: Cancer stigma, tertiary students, Punjab, social perceptions, emotional responses, survivorship, public health interventions

Introduction

Cancer is one of the biggest health challenges across the globe, both for its physical and emotional toll and for the stigma surrounding the disease. One of the social constructs of discrimination and negative perceptions (1) is the stigma attached to individuals diagnosed with cancer, which further aggravates their problems. Cancer stigma is a social process or related personal experience characterized by exclusion, rejection or blame resulting from experience or reasonable anticipation of an adverse social judgment about a person or group identified with a particular health problem. This judgment concerning the health problem is medically unwarranted (2). At its core, stigma is increasingly recognized as a fundamental determinant of health and health inequity (3).

Punjab has experienced an increasing burden of cancer, including the spate of high incidence rates reported from the "cancer belt" of Malwa (4). Despite increased

awareness campaigns, cultural and social factors remain a part of stigma, especially amongst the younger population. As future professionals and community leaders, tertiary students play a pivotal role in shaping societal attitudes toward health and disease. The presence of cancer stigma among tertiary students, who are generally at a critical stage in life for developing social norms and health literacy, can have significant consequences as well. This involves maintaining stereotypes of the disease, discouraging early detection, and promoting isolation of those living with cancer and their families (5). It is thus important to understand their perceptions and combat the stigma they may carry to create a more supportive and inclusive environment for cancer survivors and patients facing the disease.

This study delves into the prevalence and nature of cancer-related stigma among tertiary students in Punjab, exploring its origins, manifestations, and potential consequences. It seeks to identify the background pattern affecting these attitudes so that it can provide practical insights into the design of interventions aimed at promoting awareness, empathy, and health behaviour. According to the World Health Organization (6), addressing stigma is important in achieving better health outcomes for cancer patients and ensuring equal access to services.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted with data collected from 601 tertiary students across six districts in Punjab, India. The districts include Patiala, Mansa, Sangrur, Tarn Taran, Gurdaspur, and Sri Muktsar. Students from the general population of tertiary students in any of the selected districts were randomly selected. With this method, students from a wide range of educational settings were recruited, so there was no emphasis on the sample being from paving-specific institutions. The study employed a quantitative approach and a cross-sectional descriptive design. This design's benefits include the status of measured population factors and the relationships and patterns between the factors (7). The data collection instrument was a questionnaire adopted from the Cancer Stigma Scale (8).

All participants were treated with respect and ethics during the study. Before data collection started, the appropriate institution review boards were consulted to approve ethical procedures (9). Participants received comprehensive information regarding the study's goals and objectives, the procedures for participating, and their status as participants. The respondents' consent was obtained before data gathering (10). Names were removed from the data to ensure participant safety and confidentiality (11).

Four research assistants who are Punjabi natives assisted in completing the questionnaire in each designated district. Trained research assistants assisted participants and addressed survey-related enquiries. To be as comprehensive as possible within the designated districts, this study was conducted over five months. Before being added to the database, completed surveys were assigned a code. To lower the likelihood of errors, the duplicate data entry technique was used (12). The data was analyzed using Jamovi version 2.3.28. (13). Statistical methods that were both descriptive and inferential were used. The demographic information was compiled, and the stigma and beliefs around stigma among Punjabi students were examined using descriptive statistics.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Demographic Data

This section presents the demographic data of the study participants, including their district and educational level.

Table 1: Frequency Table showing Districts Selected for the Study

Frequencies of District			
District	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Gurdaspur	91	15.1 %	15.1 %
Mansa	104	17.3 %	32.4 %
Patiala	118	19.6 %	52.1 %
Sangrur	93	15.5 %	67.6 %
Tarn Taran	79	13.1 %	80.7 %
Shri Muktsar	116	19.3 %	100.0 %

Table 1 represents the districts of the study participants. The study participants were drawn from six districts within Punjab. The districts selected for the study are Gurdaspur, Mansa, Patiala, Sangrur, Tarn Taran, and Shri Muktsar. The result of the study reveals that 91 (15.1%) of the participants were from Gurdaspur, 104 (17.3%) of the participants were from Mansa, 118 (19.6%) of the participants were from Patiala, 93 (15.5%) of participants were from Sangrur; 79 (13.1%) of the participants were from Tarn Taran and 116 (19.3%) of the participants were from Shri Muktsar. Patiala has the highest number of participants, followed by Shri Muktsar. The other districts were evenly represented in this study.

Table 2: Frequency Table Showing Level of Education

Level of Education	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
undergraduate	354	58.9 %	58.9 %
Postgraduate	169	28.1 %	87.0 %
Higher	7	1.2 %	88.2 %
Others	71	11.8 %	100.0 %

Table 2 represents the level of education of the study participants. The results revealed that 354 (58.9%) of the study participants were undergraduate students; 169 (28.1) were graduate students; 7 (1.2) of the study participants were undertaking higher studies such

as PhD or Post PhD Studies; 71 (11.8%) of the study participants were undertaking studies that would lead to the award of certificate or diploma. In all, undergraduate students constituted the dominant study participants.

Stigma and Misconceptions of Cancer among Tertiary Students in Punjab

This section presented and analyzed data on stigmas and misconceptions regarding cancer among tertiary students in Punjab. These were evaluated using the Cancer Stigma Scale. Descriptive Statistics were used to analyze the data from the 601 respondents regarding cancer stigma and misconceptions.

Table 3: Frequency Table Showing the Perception that “Once you have had cancer, you can never be normal again”

Scale	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Disagree strongly	146	24.3 %	24.3 %
Disagree moderately	79	13.1 %	37.4 %
Disagree slightly	31	5.2 %	42.6 %
Agree slightly	35	5.8 %	48.4 %
Agree moderately	75	12.5 %	60.9 %
Agree strongly	211	35.1 %	96.0 %
Not sure	24	4.0 %	100.0 %

Table 3 shows responses to the statement, “Once you have had cancer, you can never be normal again”. A total of 256 respondents (42.6%) disagreed to varying degrees, while 321 respondents (53.4%) expressed varying levels of agreement. Additionally, 24 participants (4.0%) selected "Not Sure."

Cumulatively, 42.6% of respondents disagreed, while 53.4% agreed. The most significant response category was "Agree Strongly," with 211 respondents (35.1%). These findings suggest a prevalent belief that cancer survivors may struggle to regain a sense of normalcy.

Table 4: Frequency Table Showing the Perception that 'Getting cancer means mentally preparing oneself for death'

Scale	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Disagree strongly	136	22.6 %	22.6 %
Disagree moderately	76	12.6 %	35.3 %
Disagree slightly	41	6.8 %	42.1 %
Agree slightly	38	6.3 %	48.4 %
Agree moderately	79	13.1 %	61.6 %
Agree strongly	219	36.4 %	98.0 %
Not sure	12	2.0 %	100.0 %

The majority of respondents, 309 (51.8%), agreed with the statement that “getting cancer means mentally preparing for death”, while a total of 264 participants (44.0%) disagreed to varying degrees. Additionally, 12 participants (2.0%) selected "Not Sure." Thus, 44.0% of respondents disagreed cumulatively, while 51.8% agreed. The most significant response category was "Agree Strongly," with 219 respondents (36.4%). The data suggests a prevalent perception that a cancer diagnosis is associated with mentally preparing for death.

Table 5: Frequency Table showing the Perception that “A person with cancer is to blame for their condition”

Scale	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Disagree strongly	131	21.8 %	21.8 %
Disagree moderately	98	16.3 %	38.1 %
Disagree slightly	44	7.3 %	45.4 %
Agree slightly	63	10.5 %	55.9 %
Agree moderately	74	12.3 %	68.2 %
Agree strongly	141	23.5 %	91.7 %
Not sure	50	8.3 %	100.0 %

A total of 273 participants (45.4%) disagreed to varying degrees, while 278 respondents (46.3%) expressed varying degrees of agreement. Additionally, 50 participants (8.3%) selected "Not Sure."

Cumulatively, 45.4% of respondents disagreed, while 46.3% agreed. The most significant response category was "Agree Strongly," with 141 respondents (23.5%). These results highlight divided perspectives on attributing blame to individuals for their cancer diagnosis.

Table 6: Frequency Table showing the Perception that "Having cancer usually ruins a person's career"

Scale	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Disagree strongly	75	12.5 %	12.5 %
Disagree moderately	72	12.0 %	24.5 %
Disagree slightly	35	5.8 %	30.3 %
Agree slightly	87	14.5 %	44.8 %
Agree moderately	147	24.5 %	69.2 %
Agree strongly	174	29.0 %	98.2 %
Not sure	11	1.8 %	100.0 %

Table 6 summarizes beliefs about whether cancer typically wrecks someone's career. The majority of respondents agreed with the statement. A total of 408 participants (68.0%) expressed varying levels of agreement, while 182 respondents (30.3%) disagreed to some extent. Additionally, 11 participants (1.8%) selected "Not Sure."

Cumulatively, 68.0% of participants agreed, while 30.3% disagreed. The most significant response category was "Agree Strongly," with 174 respondents (29.0%). The data suggests a prevalent perception that cancer often has a detrimental effect on a person's career.

Table 7: Frequency Table showing the Perception that "Cancer usually ruins close personal relationships"

misconception6	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Disagree strongly	79	13.1 %	13.1 %
Disagree moderately	83	13.8 %	27.0 %
Disagree slightly	42	7.0 %	33.9 %
Agree slightly	65	10.8 %	44.8 %
Agree moderately	120	20.0 %	64.7 %
Agree strongly	196	32.6 %	97.3 %
Not sure	16	2.7 %	100 %

Table 7 shows that the tertiary students of Punjab strongly believe that cancer hurts close personal relationships. The responses indicate a significant level of agreement with the statement. 381 respondents (63.4%) agreed to varying degrees, while 204 participants (33.9%) expressed varying levels of disagreement. Additionally, 16 respondents (2.6%) selected "Not Sure."

Cumulatively, 63.4% of participants agreed, while 33.9% disagreed. The most significant response category was "Agree Strongly," with 196 respondents (32.6%). These results suggest a common perception that cancer can negatively impact close personal relationships.

Table 8: Frequency Table Showing the Perception that "Cancer devastates the lives of those it touches"

Scale	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Disagree strongly	87	14.5 %	14.5 %
Disagree moderately	62	10.3 %	24.8 %
Disagree slightly	49	8.2 %	32.9 %
Agree slightly	67	11.1 %	44.1 %
Agree moderately	86	14.3 %	58.4 %
Agree strongly	232	38.6 %	97.0 %
Not sure	18	3.0 %	100.0 %

The majority of respondents agreed with the statement. 385 participants (64.0%) agreed to varying degrees, while 198 respondents (32.9%) expressed some level of disagreement. Additionally, 18 participants (3.0%) selected "Not Sure."

Cumulatively, 64.0% of participants agreed, while 32.9% disagreed. The most significant response category was "Agree Strongly," with 232 respondents (38.6%). The data highlights a prevailing view that cancer profoundly impacts the lives of those affected.

DISCUSSIONS

Cancer stigma is a multifaceted phenomenon affecting the psychological and social well-being of cancer patients and is more contextual in culture-rich areas like Punjab, India. A study (14) indicates that about 60 per cent of patients reported experiencing stigma, and over one-third of patients and caregivers had internalized stigma. The findings indicate that fatalistic beliefs about cancer are prevalent, and basic education about cancer for the general public, patients, and caregivers is required. This study assessed misconceptions and attitudes towards cancer among tertiary students and the implications for patients and the community. As presented in the analyses from the Cancer Stigma Scale, all the identified themes provide valuable information on cancer stigma among tertiary students in Punjab. However, this discussion will centre on the aspects of stigma most relevant to behaviour and action affecting health behaviours, reintegration into society, and support systems for victims. These chosen themes provide an evidence-based perspective, emphasizing research from India and the world.

Misconceptions about Cancer Survivorship and Normalcy

The statement, **"Once you have had cancer, you can never be normal again"**, assessed the perceptions of the students regarding normalcy after cancer. The study results indicated that 53.4% agreed with the statement in varying degrees, which illustrates the societal view that equates survivorship with lasting disability. The notion that cancer survivors will never return to "normal" life is based on many false premises on how cancer continues to affect lives.

The results of the study align with the findings of (15), who noted that cancer survivors in India often face stigma rooted in visible and invisible effects of cancer, such as physical disabilities, emotional scars, and social isolation. Survivors often experience ongoing challenges, including fatigue, neuropathy, and cognitive changes collectively termed "chemo brain" (16). Psychologically, fear of recurrence is prevalent, contributing to anxiety and hindering reintegration into everyday life (17; 16). In India, where public awareness of survivorship care and psychosocial support remains low, these fears can

exacerbate isolation and stigmatization (Chaturvedi et al., 2015). The limited public awareness of survivorship care in India exacerbates these challenges, further marginalizing survivors (18). Cultural stigmas, particularly in collectivist societies, frame survivors as fragile and unfit for social or professional roles (19).

Cultural stigmas around illness and perceptions of diminished productivity can further isolate cancer survivors. Studies have shown that societal attitudes often frame cancer survivors as fragile or incapable, limiting their professional and social reintegration (19). In collectivist cultures like India, family and community perceptions are pivotal in shaping survivors' self-image and opportunities for returning to everyday life (20).

Despite these challenges, 42.6% of respondents disagreed with the notion that normalcy is unattainable after cancer, reflecting a growing awareness of recovery possibilities. Educational campaigns and public health initiatives that promote survivorship stories and showcase resilience can help combat negative stereotypes (21). Peer support groups, counselling, and awareness programs emphasizing long-term recovery can be instrumental in changing public perceptions (18). While misconceptions about cancer survivorship persist, increasing awareness and education about recovery, resilience, and support mechanisms can help reshape societal attitudes. Empowering survivors to share their journeys and highlighting their successes is key to challenging the belief that cancer forever alters everyday life.

Cancer and Death: A Cultural Perspective

The statement, “**Getting cancer means mentally preparing oneself for death**”, assessed the Perception of students on the association of cancer with death. 61.6% of the study participants cumulatively agreed with the statement. This underscores deeply entrenched beliefs about cancer within Indian society. Historical, cultural, and systemic factors could influence these attitudes.

This result is consistent with studies in India. (22) argue that cancer is often perceived as a terminal illness in India due to inadequate treatment services, delayed diagnosis, and limited public awareness of advancements in cancer care. This association between

cancer and death is particularly pronounced in rural and under-resourced regions, where access to timely and effective treatment is constrained, reinforcing the Perception of cancer as a death sentence (15). Cultural narratives in India have traditionally framed cancer diagnoses as catastrophic events that irrevocably change patients' lives (23). This stigma is exacerbated by societal tendencies to avoid discussions about terminal illnesses and death, as such topics are often considered taboo (18). Additionally, social pressures may lead individuals to view cancer as not just a physical condition but a moral or spiritual trial, further contributing to feelings of helplessness and resignation (19).

While urban centres in India are beginning to adopt a more hopeful view of cancer, bolstered by increasing access to advanced treatments and awareness campaigns, rural communities often lag. In these regions, the lack of healthcare infrastructure and support systems perpetuates fatalistic attitudes (15). The gap between rural and urban perceptions highlights the importance of targeted public health initiatives to challenge misconceptions and build awareness about the possibilities for recovery and improved survival rates.

Similar attitudes associating cancer with death are observed in other low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where healthcare systems face limitations in cancer detection, treatment, and survivorship care (21). In contrast, high-income countries have seen a shift in perceptions due to widespread awareness about early detection, advances in treatment, and growing numbers of cancer survivors (24). Public health campaigns in LMICs that highlight stories of survival and recovery have proven effective in challenging fatalistic narratives and encouraging early intervention (25).

Challenging the cultural Perception of cancer as synonymous with death requires a multi-pronged approach involving education, improved healthcare access, and societal dialogue. By shifting focus to narratives of survival and resilience, public health initiatives can alleviate fear, encourage early diagnosis, and foster a more supportive environment for those facing cancer diagnoses.

Culpability and Personal Responsibility for Cancer Diagnosis

Culpability involves assigning moral blame or guilt for one's condition, suggesting that individuals are responsible for their actions and the consequences of their health outcomes. This was assessed with the statement, “**A person with cancer is to blame for their condition**”. While 45.4% of respondents disagreed with the idea that patients are to blame, a comparable proportion (46.3%) expressed some level of agreement, suggesting a pervasive yet polarized societal attitude toward the issue. The most significant response category, "Agree Strongly" (23.5%), underscores the persistence of these blame narratives despite advancements in public health education.

Other statements such as, “A person with cancer is accountable for their situation”, “a person with cancer is liable for their condition”, and “If a person has cancer, it’s probably their fault” all assessed liability, accountability and culpability, which look at behavioural factors in cancer diagnosis. In all, the agreement scores of these statements were higher than the disagreement scores. This shows that most respondents agreed, in varying degrees, to the lifestyle factors in cancer and that human efforts have roles to play in such situations.

The findings of this study are consistent with practices and studies in India and many parts of the world. Blame attribution for health conditions, particularly cancer, is not uncommon in societies where lifestyle factors are heavily emphasized as primary causes of disease. In India and other similar contexts, cancer is often associated with behaviours such as smoking, alcohol consumption, and poor dietary choices (20). These beliefs can overshadow awareness of genetic predispositions, environmental exposures, and other non-modifiable risk factors that contribute to cancer development (26). The belief that cancer is a self-inflicted disease contributes to a societal stigma that isolates patients and exacerbates their psychological burden (18). Feelings of guilt and shame can deter patients from seeking social support and participating in survivorship care programs (17). Furthermore, this misconception reinforces health inequities, as it places the onus of disease prevention solely on individual behaviour, ignoring structural and environmental determinants of health.

The idea of liability often hinges on the assumption that personal behaviours directly lead to cancer, as evidenced by the higher rates of agreement with this view among those who may associate cancer with preventable behaviours. Research has demonstrated that certain lifestyle factors, such as smoking, alcohol consumption, and diet, are linked to increased cancer risk (25). For example, lung cancer is strongly associated with smoking, and the general public may perceive smokers as being responsible for their illness (27). However, this Perception fails to recognize that not all cancer cases can be explained by lifestyle factors alone, as genetics, environmental exposures, and access to healthcare play substantial roles in cancer development (28).

The persistence of such perceptions may be rooted in cultural norms that attribute health outcomes to personal discipline and moral character. In collectivist societies like India, where social norms heavily influence personal behaviour, deviation from health-related norms is often viewed through a lens of personal failure (17). The association between disease and blame is compounded by traditional health beliefs that frame illness as a consequence of lifestyle choices or even karmic justice (19).

Blame narratives can result in significant psychosocial consequences for cancer patients, including feelings of guilt, shame, and isolation (21). These emotions may prevent patients from seeking timely medical care or participating in necessary follow-up treatments (18). Additionally, patients may face social discrimination, limiting their access to emotional and financial support during their cancer journey.

Globally, efforts to reduce stigma and promote accurate cancer education have proven effective in changing public attitudes (29). However, these approaches must be culturally tailored for regions like Punjab, India, where traditional beliefs and social structures significantly influence health perceptions (20).

The findings reveal a need for continued efforts to educate the public about the complexities of cancer causation and to reduce the stigma that cancer patients often face. Public health strategies should promote compassion, dispel misconceptions, and highlight the importance of early diagnosis and holistic care for cancer patients.

Cancer and Career Impact: Employment and Discrimination

The belief that cancer often marks the end of a person's career was endorsed by 68% of survey respondents, revealing a significant stigma associated with cancer in the workplace. This belief reflects widespread concerns about survivors' ability to maintain employment due to perceived physical or cognitive limitations caused by cancer treatments. Discrimination in employment against cancer survivors is well-documented, with bias ranging from overt exclusion to subtler forms of prejudice linked to assumptions about diminished productivity or absenteeism (30).

In the Indian context, the stigma surrounding illness and disability often results in social and professional marginalization, exacerbating the challenges faced by cancer survivors in securing or maintaining employment (31). The stigma is reinforced by traditional societal expectations and workplace cultures that prioritize continuous productivity and physical presence, creating barriers for individuals who require flexible work arrangements during or after cancer treatment (17). This cultural landscape adds complexity to the already challenging experiences of cancer survivors seeking employment or career stability.

However, the survey findings also indicate a growing awareness of support systems and accommodations for cancer survivors, with 30.3% of respondents disagreeing with the statement that cancer ends a person's career. This suggests a gradual cultural shift and recognition of the importance of workplace inclusivity and accommodations. Organizations that adopt flexible work policies, such as remote work, reduced hours, or task reallocation, may provide crucial support for survivors seeking to balance recovery with professional responsibilities (32).

Globally, cancer survivors encounter similar challenges in maintaining employment, although legislative and organizational measures in many countries aim to reduce discrimination. In the United States, the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) mandates reasonable workplace accommodations for cancer survivors, contributing to reduced employment discrimination and promoting equitable access to professional opportunities (33). European countries also have legal frameworks that protect against

workplace discrimination while fostering supportive environments through paid sick leave and flexible work arrangements (34).

In India, however, the absence of robust anti-discrimination laws explicitly tailored to cancer survivors continues to pose challenges. While the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act (RPWD), 2016 covers various conditions, its applicability to cancer-related employment discrimination remains limited in practice (31). Therefore, there should be direct policies regarding the employment rights of cancer patients in India.

Cancer and Relationships/ Social Support

To assess perceptions on how the diagnosis of cancer affects relationships, the statement, "Cancer usually ruins close personal relationships" was used. The study findings reveal that 63.4% of respondents agreed variously that cancer negatively impacts close personal relationships, highlighting the multifaceted burden cancer places on patients and their social environments.

This is consistent with some studies in India. (35) noted that the emotional, psychological, and financial challenges associated with the disease often strain relationships, exacerbating feelings of isolation and limiting access to social support networks that are crucial for coping and healing. This is consistent with the research findings among the tertiary students. In the socio-cultural context of Punjab, India, perceptions around illness and disease often carry an element of stigma that can amplify relational difficulties for cancer patients. The collectivist nature of Indian society, which places high value on family and community ties, can either mitigate or intensify this stigma. While close-knit family structures may provide essential emotional and practical support, societal norms around health and illness can also lead to distancing and exclusion.

Similar trends have been observed in other Asian cultures. For instance, (36) reported that cancer patients in Japan often experience social withdrawal due to stigma, which not only isolates them but also disrupts familial and social relationships. In China, stigma and misconceptions about cancer similarly result in strained interpersonal

dynamics, impeding open communication and support from family members (37). This cultural dynamic resonates in Punjab, where public awareness about cancer's causes, treatments, and outcomes remains limited, contributing to misconceptions and stigma that exacerbate relational strains.

The importance of social support for cancer patients cannot be overstated. Studies have consistently shown that robust social networks improve patients' emotional well-being, reduce psychological distress, and enhance overall quality of life (35). In Punjab, where family members often assume traditional caregiving roles, the involvement of close relatives in a patient's care can provide both emotional support and practical assistance during treatment. However, the financial burden of cancer treatment and the stress associated with caregiving can sometimes lead to familial conflicts and emotional exhaustion.

Global research underscores the importance of fostering strong social support systems for cancer patients. For example, a study conducted in the United States found that cancer patients with strong social support networks were likelier to adhere to treatment regimens, report lower stress levels, and experience better health outcomes (38). Similarly, in European contexts, social support has been linked to improved coping strategies and reduced feelings of isolation (39).

Encouraging open conversations about cancer and reducing stigma worldwide can improve relational dynamics and ensure that patients receive the support necessary for holistic healing. Collaboration between healthcare providers, community organizations, and policymakers is essential to create inclusive systems of care that address the social dimensions of cancer.

The findings from Punjab highlight the critical need for relational and social support in cancer care. By addressing the stigma associated with the disease and fostering supportive environments for patients and their families, the emotional and relational toll of cancer can be mitigated. Integrating global lessons and local cultural understanding can lead to more effective support systems, enhancing the overall well-being of cancer patients.

Conclusion:

This study underscores the pervasive nature of cancer stigma among tertiary students in Punjab, revealing deeply ingrained misconceptions and negative perceptions. These attitudes not only hinder the emotional and social well-being of cancer survivors but also pose a barrier to early detection, treatment-seeking, and societal reintegration. Addressing these challenges is essential to foster a supportive environment that promotes awareness and compassion for individuals affected by cancer.

Recommendations:

- Implement targeted educational campaigns in tertiary institutions to debunk myths and raise awareness about cancer prevention, treatment, and survivorship.
- Facilitate workshops and interactive sessions by cancer survivors to encourage empathy and dispel stigma.
- Integrate stigma-reduction modules into health education curricula, focusing on cancer's social and psychological aspects.
- Promote collaboration between academic institutions and healthcare organizations to create support networks for students affected by cancer.

References

1. Goffman, E. (1963). *Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity*. Prentice-Hall.
2. Weiss, M. G., & Ramakrishna, J. (2006). Stigma interventions and research for international health. *The Lancet*, 367(9509), 536–538.
3. Hatzenbuehler, M. L., Phelan, J. C., & Link, B. G. (2013). Stigma is a fundamental cause of population health inequalities. *American Journal of Public Health*, 103(5), 813–821.
4. Thakur, J. S., et al. (2016). Cancer burden in the Malwa region of Punjab: Epidemiological insights. *Public Health Reports*, 14(4), 411–420.

5. Corrigan, P. W., Markowitz, F. E., & Watson, A. C. (2005). Structural levels of mental illness stigma and discrimination. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 30(3), 481–491
6. World Health Organization (WHO). (2020). *Global Report on Stigma and Discrimination in Health Care Settings*. WHO Publications.
7. Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. SAGE Publications.
8. Marlow, L. A. V., & Wardle, J. (2014). Development of a scale to assess cancer stigma in the non-patient population. *BMC Cancer*, 14, 285. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2407-14-285>
9. American Psychological Association. (2017). *Ethical principles of psychologists and code of conduct*. American Psychological Association. Retrieved from <https://www.apa.org/ethics/code>
10. Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (2019). *Principles of biomedical ethics* (8th ed.). Oxford University Press.
11. Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
12. Field, A. (2013). *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics*. SAGE Publications.
13. The jamovi project (2022). *jamovi*. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>.
14. Squiers, L. B., Rutten, L. J. F., Treiman, K., Bright, M. A., & Hesse, B. W. (2021). Cancer stigma and its impact on patients and caregivers: A national survey. *Cancer*, 127(12), 2141-2152. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.33495>
15. Gupta, S., Gumber, R., & Kumar, S. (2019). Public perceptions of cancer and its treatments in India: A study of awareness, stigma, and survivorship. *Indian Journal of Cancer Research*, 56(3), 315-321. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijc.ijc_19_19

16. Voskanyan, A., Ivanov, K., & Petrov, D. (2024). The long-term cognitive effects of chemotherapy: An updated review. *Cancer Research & Treatment*, 56(1), 87-101. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-023-07865-3>
17. Ravichandran, K., Kumar, S., & Patil, S. (2019). The impact of cultural beliefs on cancer stigma and health-seeking behaviors in India. *Journal of Cancer Education*, 34(2), 342-349. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13187-018-1409-5>
18. Chaturvedi, S. K., Strohschein, F. J., Saraf, G., & Loiselle, C. G. (2015). Communication in cancer care: Psycho-social, interactional, and cultural issues. *Aging & Mental Health*, 19(2), 111-122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2014.924097>
19. Mukherjee, S. (2020). Cultural determinants of cancer stigma: Insights from South Asian societies. *Health Sociology Review*, 29(3), 245-263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14461242.2020.1731710>
20. Gupta, A., Shridhar, K., & Dhillon, P. K. (2016). A review of breast cancer awareness among women in India: Cancer literate or awareness deficit? *European Journal of Cancer*, 51(4), 543-550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2015.10.008>
21. Lwin, M. O., Shin, W., Yee, A. Z. H., & Chan, Y. Y. (2021). Cancer stigma in Asia: Findings from a meta-analysis of prevalence and factors influencing stigma. *BMC Cancer*, 21(1), 541. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-021-08245-2>
22. Sharma, D. C., Gupta, R., & Singh, A. (2014). Public attitudes toward cancer and its treatment in India: A qualitative study. *South Asian Journal of Cancer*, 3(2), 126-132. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2278-330X.130443>
23. Chakrabarti, A. (2018). Cancer and its perception in India: Public health challenge and policy response. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*, 19(3), 759-763. <https://doi.org/10.22034/APJCP.2018.19.3.759>

24. De Boer, A. G., Taskila, T., Ojajarvi, A., Van Dijk, F. J., & Verbeek, J. H. (2015). Cancer survivors and unemployment: A meta-analysis and meta-regression. *JAMA*, 314(22), 2563-2575. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2015.6175>
25. World Health Organization (WHO). (2020). Global Report on Stigma and Discrimination
26. Anand, P., Kunnumakara, A. B., Sundaram, C., Harikumar, K. B., Tharakan, S. T., Lai, O. S., Sung, B., & Aggarwal, B. B. (2008). Cancer is a preventable disease that requires major lifestyle changes. *Pharmaceutical Research*, 25(9), 2097–2116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-008-9661-9>
27. Tindle, H. A., et al. (2012). Smoking-related stigma in lung cancer patients. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, 186(8), 763–771.
28. American Cancer Society (ACS). (2021). What causes cancer? Retrieved from www.cancer.org
29. Bower, J. E., Ganz, P. A., & Aziz, N. (2018). Fatigue and "chemo brain": Persistent side effects of cancer therapy. *Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, 58(2), 109–125
30. Paskett, E. D., Pennell, M. L., & Grady, M. M. (2018). Employment discrimination and workplace accommodations for cancer survivors: Policy implications. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention*, 27(10), 1187-1195. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-18-0452>
31. Kannan, S., & Gowda, R. (2020). Employment discrimination and cancer: A review of legal protections in India. *Indian Journal of Law and Human Rights*, 7(2), 159-174.
32. Chowdhury, T., & Jain, N. (2021). Workplace challenges and employment discrimination among cancer survivors in India. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 12(4), 123-129. <https://doi.org/10.37506/ijphrd.v12i4.16032>

33. Kreider, B., & Pepper, J. V. (2019). The impact of the Americans with Disabilities Act on employment discrimination against cancer survivors. *Health Economics*, 28(5), 719-737. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.3887>
34. Ostergaard, C. R., & Schrøder, M. (2020). Employment outcomes for cancer survivors in Europe: Legal frameworks and best practices. *European Journal of Public Health*, 30(5), 848-855. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckz132>
35. Kapur, R., Mehta, N., & Sharma, A. (2018). Cancer stigma and its impact on interpersonal relationships: A qualitative study in India. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 40(3), 225-232. https://doi.org/10.4103/IJPSYM.IJPSYM_345_17
36. Koizumi, M., Shimizu, S., & Nakatani, K. (2017). The social impact of cancer stigma in Japan: Perspectives from patients and caregivers. *Japanese Journal of Public Health*, 64(9), 743-751.
37. Chen, J., Yin, X., & Tang, Y. (2019). Social stigma and cancer in China: The role of traditional beliefs and healthcare practices. *Chinese Journal of Cancer Research*, 31(5), 863-872. <https://doi.org/10.21147/j.issn.1000-9604.2019.05.11>
38. Uchino, B. N. (2006). Social support and health: A review of physiological processes potentially underlying links to disease outcomes. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 29(4), 377-387. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10865-006-9056-5>
39. Holt-Lunstad, J., Smith, T. B., Baker, M., Harris, T., & Stephenson, D. (2010). Loneliness and social isolation as risk factors for mortality: A meta-analytic review. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 5(2), 227-237. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691610369473>